

Laboratory Work and Retention of Oscillatory Motion Concept by Physics Students in Bonny Island, Rivers State

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Abstract

This study was aimed at investigating the effect of laboratory work on Physics students' retention of oscillatory motion concept in Bonny Island, Rivers State. Quasi-experimental design research was used for the study. The study had a sample of ninety-nine (99) SS2 Physics students, selected using random sampling. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Two validated, researcher-constructed research instruments titled 'Oscillatory Motion Performance Test' with a reliability coefficient of 0.77 obtained using the Kuder-Richardson 21 formula, and 'Oscillatory Motion Retention Test' which was a reshuffled version of the first instrument, were used to collect data for the study. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that the use of laboratory work was significantly more effective than the lecture method in enabling the retention of oscillatory motion concept by students. Furthermore, a significant difference was found between the male and female students in their retention of oscillatory motion concept, in favour of the female students. The findings further revealed that the female students taught oscillatory motion using laboratory work retained most while the male students taught using lecture method retained least. The interaction of instructional method and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion was however not significant. It was therefore recommended that laboratory work should be intentionally integrated into the teaching of secondary school physics concepts.

Keywords: *Laboratory work, Oscillatory motion, Retention, Physics, Gender, Interaction.*

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Introduction

The laboratory is the power house of every science subject. It is a facility where natural phenomena is investigated, explored and explained. By the virtue of the practical work done in the laboratory, the students are provided the opportunity for hands-on and experiential learning scenario of how to be a scientist in which they experience and practice how to explore, discover and explain natural phenomena and scientific concepts. Through laboratory work, the knowledge of concepts learned in the classroom is confirmed, concretized and internalized better by the students. This enables a better and deeper understanding of scientific concepts which can be applied in real life situations outside the classroom. Laboratory work equips the students with abilities in the three domains of educational objectives, which are the cognitive domain, affective domain and psychomotor domain. The skills include the scientific process skills, observation skills, measurement skills, manipulative skills, finger dexterity, eye coordination, reflective, thinking, critical thinking, and creativity. Laboratory work also equips the students with scientific attitudes such as curiosity, honesty, open-mindedness, delayed judgement, communication and collaboration with peers, and ability to accept criticisms.

The place and role of Physics in the sustenance of mankind is very important and crucial. In Physics, matter and its relation with energy is studied. The knowledge of Physics is needed and applied knowingly or unknowingly by man at every moment of the day, even by people who are not scientific literate. Little wonder it is given an important place in the requirements for admission into Nigerian Higher institutions of learning to study many STEM careers and professions. The knowledge of Physics and its application in the bedrock of science. Every other science subject need the knowledge of Physics at one point or the other. Oscillatory motion (Simple Harmonic motion) is an important concept in Physics. Oscillation motion is a sinusoidal motion with respect to time and subjected to a restoring force. It involves and studies the characteristics of objects undergoing or performing a to-and-fro motion about a mean position. Oscillatory motion is seen in many situations in life. From the human heartbeat, to the pendulum clock, to the swings in the park for recreation, to children's toys, to big applications such as engines, to communication, to cords of musical instruments, to alternating current (electricity), and to the flapping of wings by birds, the application of oscillatory motion is experienced. However, despite the oscillatory motion in real life, the concept has been found to be a difficult concept. Many students find the concept difficult because of the peculiar characteristics of the motion, the parameters and terms involved, and the mathematical and graphical nature of the concept. This difficulty seems intercontinental as reported by researchers. In foreign studies, Somroob & Wattanakasiwich (2017) found that most students had misconceptions about restoring force, connecting mathematical solutions to real motions (especially phase angle), interpreting mechanical energy from graphs, and diagrams of Simple Harmonic motion. Dimas et al. (2018) similarly found that high school students demonstrated low ability in the multiple representation skills of simple harmonic motion, while Nugraha et al. (2019) found that most of the students only understand Simple Harmonic motion concept partially, as they had difficulty in understanding the relationship among displacement, velocity, and acceleration of the concept. In different studies investigating difficult concepts in the Physics curriculum in Nigeria, Onwioduokit (1996) found that students in Akwa Ibom state, find the concept difficult to understand, Obafemi and Onwioduokit (2013) found that senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Rivers state, find the concept difficult to understand, Bello et al. (2018) found that senior secondary school two (SS2) students

in Ife central Local Government Area, Osun State, while Adebisi et al. (2020) found that senior secondary school two 3 and 3 (SS2 and SS3) students and the teachers in Ilorin, find the concept difficult to understand and to teach.

Retention refers to the ability to retain and remember things that someone has learned or experienced over time. The ability to retain a knowledge is greatly dependent on deep understanding of concepts. Effective retention is linked with what someone has experienced. It therefore follows that the opportunity given to the students during laboratory work will enable a better and deeper understanding of Physics concepts. The essence of teaching is the ability to understand and retain the knowledge of concepts. The inability of a student to retain the knowledge of a concept learned is traceable to the method of instruction used. The conventional/ traditional lecture method of teaching has been found to be deficient and inadequate in enabling the retention of Physics concepts, especially the seemingly difficult ones such as Simple Harmonic motion concept. Chibabi et al. (2018) found a significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using laboratory teaching method and those taught using traditional teaching method, in favour of the students taught using laboratory teaching method. Okwara et al. (2019) similarly found that the students taught Basic Science using laboratory teaching method had a significantly higher mean retention score than the students taught using traditional method of teaching. On the contrary however, Abdurrahman and Garba (2014) from their study found no significant difference between the trigonometry retention scores of the slow learners taught using laboratory activity and those taught using peer tutoring teaching strategies, while Ejimonu et al. (2023) found that Computer-Simulated Strategy significantly enhanced the retention of the concept of electricity by SSI students more than Real Laboratory Experiment in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Examining the effect of gender on students' retention of scientific concepts, Abdurrahman and Garba (2014) found a significant difference between the male and female slow learners' retention abilities in trigonometry in favour of male students. Chibabi et al. (2018) similarly found a significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Biology, in favour of male students. On the contrary, Nkok (2022) found no significant influence of gender on students' retention of the concept of sexual reproduction in plants, though male students retained the concept more than female students. Obioha and Obafemi (2023) also found that at Comprehension and Application levels of Blooms taxonomy, male students retained more of the concept of Gas laws than their female counterparts, though the difference is not statistically significant at both levels. Obafemi and Macaulay (2022) however found that the female students retained more of the Electrolysis concept than the male students, though the difference is not statistically significant. Ahumaraeze and Obafemi (2025) found that the female students retained the knowledge of Algebra concept better than the male students, though the difference is not statistically significant

Concerning the joint effect of strategy and gender on the students' retention of concepts, Usman et al. (2016) found no significant joint effect of strategy and gender on the retention abilities of pre-service teachers. Ajayi and Angura (2017) found no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on the mean retention scores of students in electrolysis. Okeke (2018) found no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' retention of Chemistry concept. Obafemi and Macaulay (2022) similarly found no significant joint effect of gender and strategy on the retention Electrolysis concept by the students. Nkok (2022) found interaction of gender and teaching strategy on students' retention of the concept of sexual reproduction in plants.

Odo (2023) found no significant interaction effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention the mathematical concept of Number and Numeration. Ibeneme and Akinlabi (2021) however found a significant joint effect of strategy and gender on the retention of students, while Anari et al. (2023) found a significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' retention in Chemistry. James et al. (2024) found a significant interaction effect of method and gender on biology students' retention.

In the year 2023, WAEC Chief Examiner reported that students were not able to correctly answer questions on Simple harmonic motion (Oscillatory motion) in the 2023 in WASSCE Physics Examination due to the lack of understanding of the concept. This report confirms the fact that Simple harmonic motion is one of the Physics concepts that students find difficult to understand as discovered in the studies conducted by Obafemi and Onwioduokit (2013), Bello et al. (2018), Adebisi et al. (2020), and Taangahar and Okwori (2022). Obviously, the students will not be able to retain the knowledge of a concept that they did not understand, neither will they be able to apply the knowledge to solve real life problems. Could the use of laboratory work-based Instruction enable better understanding and subsequent retention of the concept by the students? This study therefore investigated the **effect of laboratory work-based instruction on Secondary School Physics students' retention of Oscillatory motion concept in Bonny Island, Rivers State.**

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the **effect of instructional method (laboratory work and lecture method) on Secondary School Physics students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion in Bonny Island, Rivers State.**

The followings are the specific objectives:

1. to investigate the effect of instructional method (laboratory work and lecture method) on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.
2. to investigate the influence of gender on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.
3. to determine the joint effect of instructional method (**laboratory work and lecture method**) and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of instructional method (laboratory work, lecture method) on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion?
2. What difference exist between male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion?
3. What is the joint effect of instructional method (**laboratory work and lecture method**) and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the students taught using laboratory work and those taught using lecture method in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

H₀₃: There is no significant joint effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion.

Materials and Methods

This study was aimed at investigating the effect of laboratory work on Physics students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion in Bonny Island, Rivers State. Quasi-experimental design research was used for the study. The study had a population of 1046 Senior Secondary School 2 (SS2) Physics students, out of which random sampling was used to select a sample of ninety-nine (99) SS2 Physics students comprising 38 males and 61 females from two Schools. One intact class was selected from each of two Schools for the study. The first intact class was the Experimental group while the second intact class was the Control group. Two validated, researcher-constructed research instruments titled 'Oscillatory Motion Performance Test' (OMPT) and 'Oscillatory Motion Retention Test' (OMRT) were used to collect data for the study. The performance of students in the concept of Oscillatory motion was measured using OMPT while the retention of the concept of Oscillatory motion by the students was measured using OMRT, which was a reshuffled version of OMPT. OMPT consisted of two sections A and B. Section A obtained the students' bio-data while section B contained 20 multiple choice questions on Oscillatory Motion with four options A to D. Each question was scored 1 mark totalling up to 20 marks. Kuder-Richardson 21 formula was used to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.77 for OMPT. Copies of OMPT were administered to students in each group as pre-test, after which the experimental group was taught the concept of Oscillatory motion using laboratory work while the control group was taught the same concept of Oscillatory motion using lecture method. OMPT was then re-administered to each group of students as post-test. After two weeks, OMRT was administered to the students as post-post-test. The scores of the students for pre-test, post-test and post-post-test constituted the data for this study. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the effect of instructional method (laboratory work, lecture method) on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion?

Table 1. Mean Values and Standard Deviation of Students' Retention Classified by Instructional Method

Method		Post-Test	Post-Post Test	Gain
Lab Work	Mean	14.1224	15.3265	1.2041
	N	49	49	49
	Std. Deviation	2.15670	1.96201	1.09886
Lecture Method	Mean	9.1000	6.6800	-2.4200
	N	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.24949	1.16829	1.16216

Table 1 shows that the students taught using laboratory work had a mean gain of 1.2041 while the students taught using lecture method had a mean gain of -2.4200. This indicates that the students taught using laboratory work retained the concept of oscillatory motion more than the students taught using lecture method. In other words, laboratory work was more effective than lecture method in enabling the retention of the concept of oscillatory motion by students.

Research Question 2

What difference exist between male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion?

Table 2. Mean Values and Standard Deviation of Students' Retention Classified by Gender

Gender		Post-Test	Post-Post Test	Gain
Male	Mean	12.0000	10.8947	-1.1053
	N	38	38	38
	Std. Deviation	3.27975	4.81433	1.92830
Female	Mean	11.3279	11.0000	-0.3279
	N	61	61	61
	Std. Deviation	2.93099	4.55339	2.22652

Table 2 shows that the male students had a mean gain of -1.1053 while the female students had a mean gain of -0.3279. This indicates that the female students retained the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept more than the male students.

Research Question 3

What is the joint effect of instructional method (**laboratory work and lecture method**) and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion?

Table 3. Mean Values and Standard Deviation of Students' Retention Classified by Instructional Method and Gender

Method	Gender		Post-Test	Post-Post Test	Gain
Lab Work	Male	Mean	15.1176	15.8824	0.7647
		N	17	17	17
		Std. Deviation	2.1179	2.1179	0.5623
	Female	Mean	13.5938	15.0312	1.4375
		N	32	32	32
		Std. Deviation	2.0138	1.8401	1.2427
Lecture Method	Male	Mean	9.4762	6.8571	-2.6190
		N	21	21	21
		Std. Deviation	1.1670	1.0142	1.1170
	Female	Mean	8.8276	6.5517	-2.2759
		N	29	29	29
		Std. Deviation	1.2555	1.2702	1.1921

Table 3 reveals that in the group of students taught using laboratory method, the male students had a mean gain of 0.7647 while the female students had mean gain of 1.4375, showing that the female students retained more than their male counterparts. Furthermore, in the group of students taught using lecture method, the male students had a mean gain of -2.6190 while the female students had a mean gain of -2.2759,

showing that the female students retained more than their male counterparts. These results indicate that in the two groups, the female students retained more than their male counterparts. Overall, the female students taught using laboratory work retained most while the male students taught using lecture method retained least. In other words, the retention of the knowledge of Oscillatory motion by female students taught using laboratory work is the best out of all the groups.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the students taught using laboratory work and those taught using lecture method in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Table 4. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Retention Classified by Instructional Method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-Post Test						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2002.443 ^a	2	1001.222	967.023	0.000	0.953
Intercept	16.184	1	16.184	15.631	0.000	0.140
Post-Test	152.260	1	152.260	147.060	0.000	0.605
Method	206.131	1	206.131	199.090	0.000	0.675
Error	99.395	96	1.035			
Total	13993.000	99				
Corrected Total	2101.838	98				

a. R Squared = 0.953 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.952)

Table 4 shows a value of $F_{(1,96)} = 199.090$, $p = 0.00$ ($p < 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.675 for the effect of method on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion. The null hypothesis is thereby rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the students taught using laboratory work and those taught using lecture method in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion. The partial eta squared value shows that instructional method had a large effect on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Table 5. Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Retention Classified by Instructional Method

Pairwise Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Post-Post Test						
(I) Method	(J) Method	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Lab Work	Lecture Method	5.067*	0.359	0.000	4.354	5.780
Lecture Method	Lab Work	-5.067*	0.359	0.000	-5.780	-4.354

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

As revealed by the post hoc analysis in Table 5, the mean difference between laboratory work and lecture method is 5.067. This indicates that the group of students taught using laboratory work contributed more to the significant difference in the effects of the methods on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Table 6. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Retention Classified by Gender

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-Post Test						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1822.049 ^a	2	911.024	312.586	0.000	0.867
Intercept	191.237	1	191.237	65.616	0.000	0.406
Post-Test	1821.789	1	1821.789	625.083	0.000	0.867
Gender	25.736	1	25.736	8.831	0.004	0.084
Error	279.790	96	2.914			
Total	13993.000	99				
Corrected Total	2101.838	98				
a. R Squared = 0.867 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.864)						

Table 6 shows a value of $F_{(1,96)} = 8.831$, $p = 0.004$ ($p < 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.084 for the influence of gender on students' performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is a significant difference between the male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion. The partial eta squared value shows that gender had a moderate effect on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Table 7. Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Retention Classified by Gender

Pairwise Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Post-Post Test						
(I) Gender	(J) Gender	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Female	-1.054*	0.355	0.004	-1.759	-0.350
Female	Male	1.054*	0.355	0.004	0.350	1.759
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).						

The post hoc analysis in Table 7 shows a mean difference of 1.054 between the female and male students. This indicates that the female students contributed more to the significant difference in the effect of gender on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant joint effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion.

Table 8. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Retention Classified by Instructional Method and Gender

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-Post Test						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2003.457 ^a	4	500.864	478.558	0.000	0.953
Intercept	11.684	1	11.684	11.164	0.001	0.106
Post-Test	144.096	1	144.096	137.679	0.000	0.594
Method	169.934	1	169.934	162.366	0.000	0.633
Gender	0.992	1	0.992	0.948	0.333	0.010
Method * Gender	0.052	1	0.052	0.049	0.825	0.001
Error	98.381	94	1.047			
Total	13993.000	99				
Corrected Total	2101.838	98				

a. R Squared = 0.953 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.951)

Table 8 shows a value of $F_{(1,94)} = 0.049$, $p = 0.825$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.001 for the joint effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion. The null hypothesis is thereby retained. This shows that there is no significant joint effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention of the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept. The partial eta squared value shows that instructional method and gender had a small joint effect on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that the use of laboratory work was more effective in enabling a better retention of the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept by students. There was a significant difference between the students taught using laboratory work and those taught using the lecture method in their retention of the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept, in favour of the students taught using laboratory work. Instructional method had a large effect on students' retention of the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept. This finding may be due to the fact that during laboratory work, the students worked with the materials, and in the process, concretize their knowledge of scientific concepts, resulting in their ability to retain the scientific knowledge. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Chibabi et al. (2018) and Okwara et al. (2019) who found that the students taught using laboratory teaching method had a significantly higher mean retention score than the students taught using traditional method of teaching in Biology and Basic Science respectively. This finding is however at variance with the finding of Abdurrahman and Garba (2014) who found no significant difference between the trigonometry retention scores of the slow learners taught using laboratory activity and those taught using peer tutoring teaching strategies. This finding also contradicts the finding of Ejimonu et al. (2023)

who found that Computer-Simulated Strategy significantly enhanced the retention of the concept of electricity by students more than Real Laboratory Experiment.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that the female students retained the concept of oscillatory motion more than the male students. There was a significant difference between the male and female students in their retention of the concept of oscillatory motion in favour of the female students. Gender had a moderate effect on students' retention of the knowledge of oscillatory motion concept. This finding may be due because laboratory work is gender friendly. It encouraged the female students to be active participants of the lesson which resulted in a better retention of the concept taught. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Obafemi and Macaulay (2022) who found that the female students retained more of the Electrolysis concept than the male students, and Ahumaraeze and Obafemi (2025) who found that the female students retained the knowledge of Algebra concept better than the male students. This finding is however at variance with the finding of Abdurrahman and Garba (2014) who found a significant difference between the male and female slow learners' retention abilities in trigonometry in favour of male students, and Chibabi et al. (2018) who found a significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Biology, in favour of male students. This finding is also at variance with the finding of Nkok (2022) who found no significant influence of gender on students' retention of the concept of sexual reproduction in plants, and Obioha and Obafemi (2023) who found that at Comprehension and Application levels of Blooms taxonomy, the difference between the performance of male and female students was not statistically significant.

The findings of this study further revealed that the female students taught oscillatory motion using laboratory work retained most while the male students taught using lecture method retained least. The interaction effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention of oscillatory motion was however not significant. Instructional method and gender had a small joint effect on students' retention of the concept of oscillatory motion. This finding agrees with the findings of Usman et al. (2016) who found no significant joint effect of strategy and gender on the retention abilities of pre-service teachers, Ajayi and Angura (2017) who found no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on the mean retention scores of students in electrolysis, Okeke (2018) who found no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' retention of Chemistry concept, Obafemi and Macaulay (2022) who found no significant joint effect of gender and strategy on the retention Electrolysis concept by the students, Nkok (2022) who found interaction of gender and teaching strategy on students' retention of the concept of sexual reproduction in plants, and Odo (2023) who found no significant interaction effect of instructional method and gender on students' retention the mathematical concept of Number and Numeration. The finding however is at variance the findings of Ibeneme and Akinlabi (2021) who found a significant joint effect of strategy and gender on the retention of students, Anari et al. (2023) who found a significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' retention in Chemistry, and James et al. (2024) who found a significant interaction effect of method and gender on biology students' retention.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of laboratory work on Physics students' retention of the knowledge oscillatory motion concept in Bonny Island, Rivers State. In this study,

laboratory work has been proven to be more effective in enabling the retention of the knowledge of Physics difficult concepts such as Oscillatory motion. All stakeholders concerned therefore need to encourage the effective use of laboratory work in the teaching and learning of Physics concepts. This is because laboratory work has the potential to enable a deeper understanding and consequent retention of concepts because of its engaging and hands-on and experiential nature. This will also enable the application and effective use of the knowledge acquired from the concepts to solve problems in real life situations.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Laboratory work should be intentionally integrated into the teaching of secondary school physics concepts.
2. Curriculum planners should collaborate with educators and experts to revise the Physics curriculum, placing a strong emphasis on laboratory work and hands-on experiments.
3. Government should invest in training programs for Physics teachers to enhance their ability to conduct effective laboratory sessions.

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